

DISCLAIMER

This proposal toolkit was developed by Zaz Ventures for MyScienceWork. My ScienceWork is a pioneer in open access publishing tools and develops a global visibility platform for researchers and institutions. Zaz Ventures is an innovation management consultancy and has supported over 200 customers in their public grant applications under the H2020, FP7, FP6, AAL, EUREKA, Eurostars and CIP frameworks, across a wide range of Work Programmes: ICT, Security, Transportation, Manufacturing, Health, Energy and Environment. Zaz Ventures has a strong track record with over 20 successful proposals in Horizon 2020, including in very competitive programmes where the average success rate is between 5 and 10%. Follow us on @h2020experts and contact us at euproject@zazventures.com for proposal writing support.

OPEN ACCESS PUBLISHING IN HORIZON 2020

European Union member states released in May 2016 a [joint statement](#) on an ambitious new open access target, whereby scientific publications on the results of research supported by public and public-private funds **must be** freely accessible to everyone by year 2020.

Despite the current open access requirements of H2020, true open access is not a reality yet. Many consortia continue to publish their results in closed access magazines or use unnecessary long embargo periods before publishing in open access media.

This renewed commitment from the European Union to open access means that the European Commission will now enforce much more strictly the open access requirements of H2020, starting with the evaluation of H2020 applications. In practice, evaluators will be requested to evaluate if the open access strategy outlined in the proposals they are reviewing is adequately described, and can truly enable the open access goals set by the European Union.

"The days of keeping our research results to ourselves are over. There is far more to gain from sharing data and letting others access and analyse that data.

For example, if sharing big data reveals that a certain kind of cancer activates a particular molecular pathway in most cases and it turns out that there is already a drug approved and available to block the activation of that molecular pathway, clinical trials can begin almost immediately. Saving time, money and lives.

Or if scientists want to monitor the effects of climate change on local ecosystems, they can use Open Science to engage citizen reporting, and rapidly multiply the data at their disposal.

To make the most of Open Science opportunities for Europe, I plan to focus on open data, open access and research integrity over the course of my mandate."

Commissioner Carlos Moedas,
"European research and innovation for global challenges", Lund, 4 December 2015

Open science: opening up the research process (source: Open Innovation, Open Science, Open to the World – a vision for Europe, May 2016, ISBN 978-92-79-57346-0, doi:10.2777/061652)

OPEN DATA MANAGEMENT IN HORIZON 2020

Projects participating in the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot will be required to develop a Data Management Plan (DMP), in which they will specify what data will be kept for the longer term. Other projects are invited to submit a Data Management Plan if it is relevant for their planned research.

One of the recommended tool is [DMPonline](#), which offers DMP templates that match the demands and suggestions of the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020.

The first version of the DMP is expected to be delivered within the first 6 months of the project. More elaborated versions of the DMP can be delivered at later stages of the project. The DMP should be updated at least by the mid-term and final review to fine-tune it to the data generated and the uses identified by the consortium since not all data or potential uses are clear from the start. New versions of the DMP should be created whenever important changes to the project occur due to inclusion of new data sets, changes in consortium policies or external factors.

OFFICIAL H2020 PROPOSAL TEMPLATES

Horizon 2020 application templates are requesting specific commitments from the applicants covering both open data management and open access publishing.

Open access publishing

Proposers must outline the strategy for knowledge management and protection, including measures to provide open access (free on-line access, such as the 'green' or 'gold' model) to peer-reviewed scientific publications which might result from the project.

Open access must be granted to all scientific publications resulting from Horizon 2020 actions.

 *Open access publishing (also called 'gold' open access) means that an article is **immediately** provided in open access mode by the scientific publisher. The associated costs are usually shifted away from readers, and instead (for example) to the university or research institute to which the researcher is affiliated, or to the funding agency supporting the research.*

 Self-archiving (also called 'green' open access) means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived by the researcher - or a representative - in an online repository before, after or alongside its publication. Access to this article is often - but not necessarily - delayed ('embargo period'), as some scientific publishers may wish to recoup their investment by selling subscriptions and charging pay-per-download/view fees during an exclusivity period.

Further references: Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

This is a **hard** requirement, meaning that open access is mandatory for all scientific publications resulting from Horizon 2020 actions, and that proposals not providing enough evidence of their open access commitment will be impacted negatively during the evaluation process.

Open data management

If they take part in the pilot on Open Research Data, proposer must include information on how the participants will manage the research data generated and/or collected during the project, in particular addressing the following issues:

- What types of data will the project generate/collect?
- What standards will be used?
- How will this data be exploited and/or shared/made accessible for verification and re-use? If data cannot be made available, explain why.
- How will this data be curated and preserved?

Further references: Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

This is a **soft** requirement, meaning that participation to the pilot on Open Research Data is voluntary and (in theory) should not influence the evaluation of your application.

PROPOSAL TOOLKIT

In order to fulfil the open access publishing and open data access requirements of Horizon 2020, and therefore to maximize the chances for your proposal to be evaluated positively for funding, we recommend the inclusion of the following components in the Part B of your proposal. If you are unclear as how to use this toolkit, please do not hesitate to contact us at h2020@mysciencework.

Section 2.2 a) (dissemination of project results)

The following paragraph should be adapted to your needs and inserted in section 2.2 a) of the proposal.

[Project XXX] will strictly follow the open access policy of Horizon 2020 by providing on-line access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and that is re-usable. In the context of this project, scientific information refers to peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals), pre-print articles, conference papers, patents, books and research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

Open access to scientific peer reviewed publications has been anchored as an underlying principle in the Horizon 2020 and is explained in the Regulation and the Rules of Participation as well as through [Article 29.2 of the Model Grant Agreement](#). The consortium will use an Institutional Open Repository to store and provide access to scientific publication and researchers profiles. This repository will automatically feed OpenAIRE with articles to ensure the largest possible impact among researchers, policy-makers and businesses.

Each consortium partner commits to deposit as soon as possible and at the latest on publication. Each partner will ensure open access to the deposited publication (via the repository) at the latest on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or within six months of publication [twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities] in any other case.

Each consortium partner will also ensure access to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication (including the terms European Union (EU) and Horizon 2020; the name of the action, acronym and grant number; the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and a persistent identifier). However, the partners will retain their copyright and grant adequate licences to publishers, based on Creative Commons licences.

The following paragraph is optional and can be disregarded if you are not planning to participate to the open data pilot.

Optional: open data pilot

The consortium will voluntarily participate in the Open Data Pilot. Data management activities are part of task X.X and will start with the formal release of a Data Management Plan (D X.X) at M6. The project will follow the open data management guidelines of the Horizon 2020 Programme and specifically:

- The project will deposit the research data in a research data repository that facilitates linking publications and underlying data through persistent identifiers and data citations.*
- The project will take to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) this research data by attaching Creative Commons Licences to the data deposited*
- The project will provide information via the research repository about the tools available to the users that are needed to validate the results, e.g. specialised software or software*

code, algorithms and analysis protocols, and wherever possible, will provide these instruments.

Section 2.2 b) (communication of project results)

The following paragraph should be adapted to your needs and inserted in section 2.2 b) of the proposal.

The coordinator will implement an open access project portal enabling the consortium to easily store publications, communicate about the project, disseminate project results and federate a community of partners.

The portal will centralize all project-related publications (scientific articles, pre-prints, patents or conference publications, presentation, etc.) in a dedicated institutional repository, together with automatically populated structured metadata. The portal will include a built-in validation workflow for project administrators to check and validate the publication import, its metadata and license information. The portal will be fully integrated with OpenAIRE, enabling the automatic transfer of publications to OpenAIRE in order to maximize open access dissemination capabilities.

Dissemination methodologies will include scientific publications, generalist publications, conference posters & speeches and participation to industry events. The communication plan will use specific social media tools such as MyScienceWork.com, Twitter, LinkedIn, Reddit and Storify). The communication activities will include medias such as the [Horizon 2020 newsroom](#), the [research*eu results](#) magazine, the [research*eu focus](#) magazine and other [EC publications](#) as applicable.

The project visibility will be ensured through search engine optimization (SEO), in order to make sure that the project results are well referenced by traditional search engines like Google, Bing, Yahoo, Ask, etc. The underlying platform (Polaris) has a partnership with Google Scholar that will enhance the discoverability of the project publications.

Publishing activities will be monitored with specific metrics (most read or most downloaded publications, most read authors, license type, journals, publication type, geographical distribution of the audience).

The portal will also support the development of a partner community. The portal will include a scientific profile for each project researchers, allowing them to join the global MyScienceWork community, which is represented by 500,000 academic and industrial members from 211 countries, working and interested in all scientific disciplines.

Section 3.1 (work package description)

The following paragraph should be adapted to your needs and inserted in the relevant work package table in section 3.1 of the proposal. Text in italic is only for projects opting in the open data pilot.

Description of work
Task X.X: Developing the project website (lead: XXX, contributors: all) This task will focus on the development of the project website. The website will include a description of the project, the consortium and the workplan. It will also contain a list of public deliverables from the project, together with relevant related scientific news. It will be fully integrated with the social media tools used in the project.
Task X.X: Developing and implementing the dissemination plan (lead: XXX, contributors: all)

This task will focus on the dissemination strategy and plan of the project results through a variety of channels. At the beginning of the project, the project consortium will specify produce a dissemination plan, which will be re-assessed and refined periodically. During the project, the consortium will ensure the dissemination of all publications, messages and projects outcomes to get maximum visibility at local, national and international levels. Dissemination methodologies will include scientific publications, generalist publications, conference posters & speeches and participation to industry events. The communication plan will use specific social media tools such as MyScienceWork.com, Twitter, LinkedIn, Reddit and Storify). The communication activities will include medias such as the [Horizon 2020 newsroom](#), the [research*eu results](#) magazine, the [research*eu focus](#) magazine and other [EC publications](#) as applicable. The project visibility will be ensured through search engine optimization (SEO) and a partnership with Google Scholar that will enhance the discoverability of the project publications. Publishing activities will be monitored with specific metrics (most read or most downloaded publications, most read authors, license type, journals, publication type, geographical distribution of the audience).

Task X.X: Managing open data and open access publications (lead: ORE, contributors: all)

The task will set up a dedicated open access repository, integrated with the global MyScienceWork.com environment. The repository will include two components, one focusing on publication and the other on data. In addition to the open access journals they are published in, all publications will join the MyScienceWork global database of over 30M scientific publications and be visible by the large community of MyScienceWork members (500,000 researchers, science journalist, science fans, founders, industry partners, etc.). The dedicated open access repository will centralize all project-related publications (scientific articles, pre-prints, patents or conference publications, presentation, etc.) in a dedicated institutional repository, together with automatically populated structured metadata. The portal will include a built-in validation workflow for project administrators to check and validate the publication import, its metadata and license information. The open access repository will be fully integrated with OpenAIRE, enabling the automatic transfer of publications to OpenAIRE in order to maximize open access dissemination capabilities. *The task will also result in a data management plan delivered at M6 and updated throughout the project, whenever important changes to the project occur due to inclusion of new data sets, changes in consortium policies or external factors.*

Deliverables

From task	ID	Name	Lead	Main contributors	Diss. level	Delivery month
X.X	DX.X	Project website	XXX	All partners	PU	M3
X.X	DX.X	Open access repository	XXX	All partners	PU	M3
X.X	DX.X	Dissemination plan	XXX	All partners	CO	M6
X.X	DX.X	Interim dissemination report	XXX	All partners	PU	M12
X.X	DX.X	Interim dissemination report	XXX	All partners	PU	M24
X.X	DX.X	Interim dissemination report	XXX	All partners	PU	M36
X.X	DX.X	Final dissemination report	XXX	All partners	PU	MXX
X.X	DX.X	<i>Data management plan</i>	XXX	<i>All partners</i>	CO	M6
X.X	DX.X	<i>Data management plan update</i>	XXX	<i>All partners</i>	CO	MXX
X.X	DX.X	<i>Data management plan update</i>	XXX	<i>All partners</i>	CO	MXX
X.X	DX.X	<i>Data management plan update</i>	XXX	<i>All partners</i>	CO	MXX

Section 3.4 (resources to be committed)

The following budget should be reserved to support open access requirements. Select the options you require and insert the rows in Table 3.4 'Other direct cost' items (travel, equipment, other goods and services, large research infrastructure).

The Coordinator should use Option 1 in all cases and choose between Option 2a (recommended for Innovation Actions) and Option 2b (recommended for Research & Innovation Actions). The budgeted figures are based on the use of the Polaris platform (licensed by MyScienceWork), and additional communication services provided by MyScienceWork (Communication Packages).

All academic/research partners should use Option 3 based on the number of publications they are planning to lead (note that publications might be co-authored by multiple partners but only one organization will support the open access publication fee for a given publication).

All budgeted costs are eligible other direct costs for any Horizon 2020 project, and can be treated as cost of goods and services (as per Article 10 of the [Annotated Grant Management Agreement](#)) i.e. do not require subcontracting agreements with the product/service supplier.

Please note that open access publication fees vary widely between media, so you should check that the budgeted amount is aligned with the average costs observed in your field of research¹.

[Coordinator]	Cost (€)	Justification
Open access infrastructure	1,150 x (number of project months)	The open access communication infrastructure will use a SaaS license such as Polaris from MyScienceWork, including user access for up to 250 researchers.
Open access publication costs	3,500 x (number of planned publications led by the partner)	The largest publishers of Open Access journals charge between €1,000 and €5,000 to publish peer-reviewed articles. For budgeting purposes, we have retained an average publishing fee of €3,500.

Option 1: standard coordinator infrastructure and publication costs

[Coordinator]	Cost (€)	Justification
Communication Package	1,290 x (number of project quarter)	Polaris Communication Package including 1 popularized article and 1 interview short video through web technology per quarter

Option 2a: additional coordinator communication costs (low intensity)

[Coordinator]	Cost (€)	Justification
Communication Package	3,690 x (number of project quarter)	Polaris Communication Package including 3 popularized articles and 3 interviews short video through web technology per quarter

Option 2b: additional coordinator communication costs (high intensity)

¹ Further references: <http://www.nature.com/news/open-access-the-true-cost-of-science-publishing-1.12676#/rise> and <http://blog.scielo.org/en/2013/09/18/how-much-does-it-cost-to-publish-in-open-access/>

[Partner XXX]	Cost (€)	Justification
Open access publication costs	3,500 x (number of planned publications led by the partner)	The largest publishers of Open Access journals charge between €1,000 and €5,000 to publish peer-reviewed articles. For budgeting purposes, we have retained an average publishing fee of €3,500.

Option 3: standard partner publication costs